

Effect of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Perceived Price to Repurchase Intention: Mediating Role of Perceived Trust

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived price and perceived trust on repurchase intentions with perceived trust as an intervening variable. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a total of 155 respondents who use Gofood application. Collecting data using an online questionnaire with a Likert Scale. This study uses the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method through the smartPLS 3.0 program to process data. The results showed that perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and perceived price had a positive and significant effect on perceived trust, perceived usefulness had a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions, perceived ease of use had an effect positive and not significant on repurchase intention, perceived price has a positive and not significant effect on repurchase intention, and perceived trust has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. The perceived trust variable as a mediator can strengthen between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and perceived price to repurchase intention.

Keywords:- Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Price, Perceived Trust, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this era, internet technology has become something that cannot be ignored in business development. It is a powerful tool that businesses can use to gain an advantage. The rapid development of technology with rapid growth of internet users has become an opportunity for business people.

Research from Emarketers.com (2020) said research institute and data provider based in New York, Indonesia has a rapid growth of new internet users every year. Online sales are expected to continue to increase and take up a larger share of retail trade. Indonesia in 2021 reach 202.6M users with a penetration of 74% of Indonesia's total population of 274.9 million. (Hootsuite, 2021).

Consumers are usually happy because they no longer need to come to the store to buy a product. Consumers from almost every country now benefit from making transactions online. In 2021, more than two billion people buy goods or services online (www.statista.com).

Due to the increasing growth in internet use from year to year which of course encourages e-commerce penetration which continues to penetrate various sectors, this is utilized by Gofood as an opportunity in online food delivery services. When someone is stuck with a busy schedule, people don't have time to go out to buy food. Because of that, Gojek has created a service to support this case called Gofood. Based on existing phenomenon, the author need to research on what factors can influence customers to want to make repurchase intention in Gofood. From the result of the preliminary survey, four variable have the highest value were obtained, which are perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived price which will be used as independent variables. And perceived trust as a mediation variable.

II. LITERATURE

A. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

TAM is commonly used in understanding the relationship between users and acceptance of technology through various perceptions. This theory come from Davis M (1986) and then used and developed again by several scientists such as Adam et al. (1992) Szajna (1994), Igbaria et al. (1995) and Venkatesh and Davis (2000). TAM is often considered a common and powerful model for consumer acceptance of innovative technologies (GarcíaPeñalvo 2015;and Hubert et al. 2017). TAM affects behavioral intention to use something. Natarajan et al (2018) define that TAM can be considered as the main research stream in exploring the determinants of behavior in receiving and using information systems.

B. Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness is “the extent to which a person believes that using a particular technology will improve his job performance,” (Davis 1989). In other words, the extent to which system users are optimistic that productivity and effectiveness in their work can be increased through the use of the system (Mou, Shin, & Cohen, 2016). According to Corkindale, Ram, and Chen (2018), perceived usefulness measures a person's belief that using a system will help him do their job better. People can stay to use a system if they believe that system can be useful for them, and conversely people will choose not to use it if they believe that the system is not useful (Jogiyanto, 2007).

C. Perceived Ease of Use

Websites or applications that are easy to use by consumers will be preferred by consumers, because they don't need to spend a lot of time to studying them (Dawi et al., 2018). Perceived ease of use is part of TAM (Cho & Son, 2019) where part of this model is commonly used in research related to the use of new technology. Zeba & Ganguli (2016) Perceived ease of use define where users believe that an innovation can help them do a better job.

D. Perceived Price

According to P. Kotler and G. Armstrong (2009) price refers the amount of money charged for a product or service. While perceived price is the consumer's perception of the relative price that must be spent to obtain a product or service compared to the price of other similar products. Perceived price is the relationship between price and (Chapman, 2016). Erickson and Johansen (1985) state price as a currency must be sacrificed by consumers from their purchased.

E. Perceived Trust

Perceived trust is a key for customer development and building strong and long-term relationships businesses (Santos and Fernandes, 2008). Perceived trust is consumer confidence in a company or product. Confidence in online buying and selling transactions will arouse consumer interest in making purchases online (Hidayat et al., 2020). Conversely, lack of trust is the biggest barrier for consumers to make transactions. (Urban et al., 2009). (Lingling Gao, 2017), when a customer makes an intention to buy, the consumer will read reviews on websites, forums, and blogs, to make sure the purchase intention is correct.

F. Repurchase Intention

According to Lin & Liang (2011) repurchase intention is the extent to which customers are willing to buy the same product or service based on what is observed from previous purchases. Repurchase intention refers to willingness of consumers who have completed their purchase and can make it back to the same company in the future with various considerations. (Kuan, Bock, & Vathanophas, 2008). According to Chiang (2016), repurchase intention is a customer's willingness to repurchase a product/service after it has been used. In the service context, it can be considered as an intention to revisit or make a reservation again (Bilgihan & Bujisic, 2015).

Repurchase intention can be defined “an individual's judgment about buying a service again, a decision to engage in a future activity with a service provider and what form this activity will take” (Wilson, 2019).

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on library studies and previous research, the study model and the relationships between the variables were built in figure 1.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Figure 1, illustrates the study model and the study hypotheses were formulated :

- H1: Perceived usefulness has a positive and significant influence on perceived trust
- H2: Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant influence on perceived trust
- H3: Perceived price has a positive and significant influence on perceived trust
- H4: Perceived usefulness has a positive and significant influence on repurchase intention
- H5: Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant influence on repurchase intention
- H6: Perceived price has a positive and significant influence on repurchase intention
- H7: Perceived trust has a positive and significant influence on repurchase intention
- H8: The relationship between perceived usefulness and repurchase intention is mediated by perceived trust
- H9: The relationship between perceived ease of use and repurchase intention is mediated by perceived trust
- H10: The relationship between perceived price and repurchase intention is mediated by perceived trust

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this study author used quantitative methods. The research used an online questionnaire link via social media such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and Telegram for people who use Gofood application. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a total of 177 respondents. This study use the SEM method through the smartPLS 3.0 program to process data.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Respondent characteristic data was obtained from a Respondent was obtained from a online questionnaire that had been distributed to 155 respondents domiciled in Indonesia. The structural model was evaluated accordance with the hypothesized effect in our research model.

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	CA	CR	AVE
Perceived Usefulness	PU1	0,861	0.906	0.934	0.780
	PU2	0,900			
	PU3	0.891			
	PU4	0.880			
Perceived Ease of Use	PEOU1	0,821	0.884	0.920	0.742
	PEOU2	0,891			
	PEOU3	0,853			
	PEOU4	0,879			
Perceived Price	PP1	0,854	0.853	0.901	0.694
	PP2	0,809			
	PP3	0,829			
	PP4	0,839			
Perceived Trust	PT1	0,814	0.892	0.925	0.756
	PT2	0,881			
	PT3	0,899			
	PT4	0,882			
Repurchase Intention	RI1	0,838	0.887	0.922	0.747
	RI2	0,881			
	RI3	0,872			
	RI4	0,865			

Table 1: Construct Reliability and Validity Results

According to Hair, et al. (2021), the value for outer loadings > 0.7. Based on table 1, that the AVE value of all variables in each indicator is > 0.5. So it can be stated that each variable has good convergent validity.

Another assessment of the indicator is the reliability to find out the indicator consistency when the measurement is performed at different times. Reliability testing uses Cronbach's alpha (CA) and Composite reliability (CR) values. As shown in Table 1, Cronbach's alpha value of five variables is between 0.853 - 0.906. Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.7, so all variables are considered reliable based on Cronbach's alpha value. The composite reliability value of the five variables is between 0.901 - 0.934. The value of composite reliability is above 0.7, so all variables are declared reliable based on composite reliability (Hair et al., 2021).

Variable	R-Square	Q-Square
PERCEIVED TRUST	0.734	0.542
REPURCHASE INTENTION	0.627	0.456

Table 2: Coefficient of determination (R2) & (Q2)

In Table 2, the R-Square value for the repurchase intention variable is 0.627 which means that 62.7% of the repurchase intention variable can be explained by the variables perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived price and perceived trust. And the R-Square value on the mediating variable perceived trust is 0.734, which means that 73.4% of the variable perceived trust can be explained by the variable perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and perceived price.

Besides the Q-square values, the test indicates that perceived trust and repurchase intention values are greater than zero (Table 2), indicating adequate predictive validity of the model (Henseler et al., 2009). Accordingly, enough predictive validity for the structural model was also confirmed.

In Table 3 explain the hypothesis test results, given the values and the relevant significance.

Research Hypothesis		T-Statistic	P-Value	Results
H1	PERCEIVED USEFULNESS → PERCEIVED TRUST	2.927	0.004	Positive and Significant
H2	PERCEIVED EASE OF USE → PERCEIVED TRUST	5.953	0.000	Positive and Significant
H3	PERCEIVED PRICE → PERCEIVED TRUST	4.430	0.000	Positive and Significant
H4	PERCEIVED USEFULNESS → REPURCHASE INTENTION	2.807	0.005	Positive and Significant
H5	PERCEIVED EASE OF USE → REPURCHASE INTENTION	1.872	0.062	Positive and not Significant
H6	PERCEIVED PRICE → REPURCHASE INTENTION	0.991	0.322	Positive and not Significant
H7	PERCEIVED TRUST → REPURCHASE INTENTION	3.089	0.002	Positive and Significant
H8	PERCEIVED USEFULNESS → PERCEIVED TRUST → REPURCHASE INTENTION	2.336	0.020	Positive and Significant

H9	PERCEIVED EASE OF USE → PERCEIVED TRUST → REPURCHASE INTENTION	2.629	0.009	Positive and Significant t
H10	PERCEIVED PRICE → PERCEIVED TRUST → REPURCHASE INTENTION	2.432	0.015	Positive and Significant t

Table 3: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results in Table 3, the perceived usefulness variable can have a positive and significant effect on perceived trust. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 2.927 and p-value is 0.004, which is greater than the minimum limit value, (t-statistic >1.96 and the p-value > 0.005) so H1 is supported.

The perceived ease of use variable have a positive and significant effect on perceived trust. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 5.953 and p-value is 0.000, which is greater than the minimum limit value, (t-statistic >1.65 and the p-value > 0.005) so H2 is supported.

The perceived price variable have a positive and significant effect on perceived trust. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 4.430 and p-value is 0.000, which is greater than the minimum limit value, (t-statistic >1.65 and the p-value > 0.005) so H3 is supported.

The perceived usefulness variable have a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 2.807 and p-value is 0.005, which is greater than the minimum limit value (t-statistic >1.65 and the p-value > 0.005) so H4 is supported.

The perceived ease of use variable have a positive and not significant effect on repurchase intention. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 1.872 and p-value is 0.062, which is (t-statistic >1.65 and the p-value > 0.005) so H5 is rejected.

The perceived price variable have a positive and not significant effect on repurchase intention. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 0.991 and p-value is 0.322, which is (t-statistic >1.65 and the p-value > 0.005) so H6 is rejected.

The perceived trust variable have a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 3.089 and p-value is 0.002, which is greater than the minimum limit value (t-statistic >1.65 and the p-value > 0.005) so H7 is supported.

The mediated perceived trust between perceived usefulness and repurchase intention is positive and significant. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 2.336 and p-value is 0.020, so H8 is supported.

The mediated perceived trust between perceived ease of use and repurchase intention is positive and significant. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 2.629 and p-value is 0.009, so H9 is supported.

The mediated perceived trust between perceived price and repurchase intention is positive and significant. This is evident from the t-statistics value of 2.432 and p-value is 0.015, so H10 is supported.

VI. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The results showed that perceived usefulness, ease of use, and price had a positive and significant on perceived trust, perceived usefulness had a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions, perceived ease of use had an effect positive and not significant on repurchase intention, perceived price has a positive and not significant effect on repurchase intention, and perceived trust has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. The perceived trust variable as a mediator can strengthen between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and perceived price to repurchase intention.

Based on the result, Gofood needs to further improve its services, especially in the field of internet technology, because current technological developments will continue to develop. Meanwhile, to improve perceived price, Gofood needs to monitor prices set, so the prices set are not too high or too low. And its hoped that Gofood can further improve quality in responding to consumer complaints, so that consumers not feel worried if there is a problem with their purchase. Gofood can guarantee the security of the data provided by customers so that consumers can feel safer making purchases on the Gofood application.

This research has a limitation because only uses variables of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived price, and perceived trust to repurchase intention. So for further researchers can add other variables such as consumer satisfaction and loyalty variables, so that more variables can be identified. In addition, future researchers can increase the number of samples with a wider coverage area.

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